

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MULTIPLE PRIMARY MALIGNANT TUMORS OF COLORECTUM AND LUNG

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ABSTRACT

Multiple primary malignant tumors of the colorectal and lung are extremely rare and are mostly diagnosed incidentally. Due to their low incidence, most clinicians assume pulmonary lesions in patients with proven colon adenocarcinoma as lung metastases. We describe a case of a 69-year-old man with complaints of rectal bleeding accompanied by chronic constipation. Biopsy examination of the colorectal area was diagnosed with colon adenocarcinoma. Subsequent CT examination revealed a tumor mass in the right lung, assessed as a metastasis from colon carcinoma. VATS biopsy was performed with the result of poorly differentiated carcinoma with solid structure. Subsequent IHC examination excluded lung metastasis from colon adenocarcinoma. The immunophenotype of the tumor was consistent with large cell neuroendocrine lung carcinoma.

Keywords: multiple primary malignant tumors, colorectal carcinoma, large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the lung.

Introduction

Colorectal carcinoma (CRC) is one of the leading causes of cancer-related deaths in Europe [4]. Around 10–15% of all CRC patients develop pulmonary metastases [11]. There is a subset of CRC patients with lung metastases who are potentially resectable. In this patient group, curative resection of lung metastases can lead to long-term survival [7, 9].

Large cell neuroendocrine tumors (LCNET) are a very uncommon type of colon cancer that tends to have a poor prognosis. Usually, these tumors are only found at the time of metastasis making them even more difficult to treat. The histological features of LCNETs are characterized by neuroendocrine appearance under light microscopy - organoid, nesting, trabecular, rosette, and palisading pattern, large cells with a polygonal shape, ample cytoplasm, coarse chromatin, and frequent nucleoli, very high mitotic rate along with frequent necrosis and evidence of neuroendocrine features by immunohistochemistry [3].

Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the lung (LCNEC) is a rare and highly aggressive type of lung cancer, with a complex biology that shares similarities with both small-cell lung cancer (SCLC) and non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC). The diagnosis of LCNEC requires the identification of neuroendocrine morphology and the expression of at least one of the neuroendocrine markers - chromogranin A, synaptophysin or CD56 [1]. The most sensitive neuroendocrine biomarker is NCAM/CD56, expressed in 92–98% of cases [8].

Multiple primary malignant tumors of lung and colorectal incidence were extremely rare and in most cases, diagnosed incidentally. Due to its rarity, most physicians consider pulmonary lesions found in patients with a history of colorectal cancer as lung metastasis [6].

Material and methods

The histologic specimens were made with fixation of 10% neutral formalin and embedded in paraffin. The cut sections were 4 mkm thick and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (HE). Immunohistochemical tests for SATB2, CD56, TTF1, p40, Synaptophysin were performed.

Results

The patient's first biopsy was performed in the Surgical Department of Svilengrad General Hospital in December 2023. Gastroscopy and colonoscopy were performed due to rectal bleeding and chronic constipation.

The result of the biopsy examination of a fragment of gastric mucosa showed evidence of erosive erythemo-exudative gastritis, with focal and confluent hemorrhages, reactive foveolar hyperplasia, moderate inflammatory infiltration, focal intestinal metaplasia, negative for *Helicobacter pylori*. (BN№ 645/2023).

During colonoscopy, in the rectosigmoid region, an area with an uneven surface, bleeding easily when touched, covered with purulent exudate is encountered. Biopsy examination of material from this area (BN№ 646/2023) presents hyperplastic colonic mucosa with purulent-hemorrhagic exudate in the submucosa,

among which single tumor glands of moderately differentiated colonic adenocarcinoma are encountered

(Fig.1), with the presence of solid tumor structures (Fig. 2).

Glandular structures of moderately differentiated colon adenocarcinoma - magn.x40, (Fig.1)

Fragments of moderately differentiated colon adenocarcinoma with solid areas (bottom right) - magn.x40, (Fig.2)

Six months later, the patient was admitted to "Kaspela" University hospital Plovdiv for biopsy clarification of a volumetric formation in the right lung, identified on CT of the lung and mediastinum - native scanning. The tumor measured 28/15 mm, located in the right perihilar, with infiltration of the adjacent bronchus. A single enlarged lymph node measuring 13/8 mm was also identified precarinally. The conclusion of the CT scan was that it was a metastasis in the right lung. The fiber-optic bronchoscopy did not achieve histological verification of the process. After discussion

by a clinical council, a decision was made for surgical verification. Under general intubation anesthesia, after thorough cleaning of the surgical field, VATS was performed on the right. A pin biopsy was taken from the tumor formation located in the second segment. The result of the biopsy examination (K-24-2300 / 12.02.24) shows fragments of lung tissue with infiltration of poorly differentiated carcinoma with solid structure (Fig. 3). Tumor complexes with initial vascular inva-

sion are encountered. Lymphocytic inflammatory infiltration and the presence of anthracotic (black) pigment are detected on the periphery (Fig. 4).

Low-grade solid carcinoma - magn.x40, (Fig. 3)

Low-grade carcinoma, with initial vascular invasion - magn.x40, (Fig. 4)

Due to the presence of solid identical areas with similar tumor cell morphology in biopsies from colon and lung carcinoma (Fig.2 and Fig.4), IHC examination was performed. The immunohistochemical tests showed negative expression of SATB2, TTF1, p40, Synaptophysin and focal positive staining for CD56 (Fig. 5).

Undifferentiated lung carcinoma – focal positive staining for CD 56 - magn.x40, (Fig.4)

The IHC result ruled out pulmonary metastasis from colon adenocarcinoma. The immunophenotype of the tumor was consistent with large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of the lung.

Discussion

Histological/Cytological diagnosis of LCNEC is complex because small biopsies are usually insufficient due to crushing artifacts, whereas a surgical lung biopsy is usually required. LCNEC appears as a high-grade malignant tumor with neuroendocrine morphology (organoid or trabecular patterns, rosette-like structures, or peripheral palisading), a non-small-cell cytology (with a cell size three times larger than lymphocytes diameter), abundant cytoplasm (often eosinophilic), prominent nucleoli and low nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio [2].

Most of the patients with LCNEC (40–50%) are diagnosed with metastatic diseases [12]. In the case presented by us, LCNEC was diagnosed at an early stage and the CT finding was metastasis from colon adenocarcinoma to the right lung. Multiple primary malignant “Synchronous” tumors refer to cases in which the second primary cancer is diagnosed within 6 months of the primary cancer. Multiple primary malignant “metachronous” tumors refer to cases in which the second primary cancer is diagnosed more than 6 months after the diagnosis of the first primary cancer. [10]

Depending on the histological variant of the lung carcinoma, in some cases it is appropriate to conduct additional testing after immunohistochemical verification to identify mutations activating the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR). [5]

Conclusion

In multiple primary malignant tumors, there are borderline variants between „Synchronous” and „Metachronous” tumors. In these borderline variants, the second malignant tumor is diagnosed exactly 6 months

after the first malignant tumor is detected and it is not possible to assign it to one group or the other.

For the accurate diagnosis of cases with multiple primary malignant tumors, including non-small cell lung carcinomas, after precise immunohistochemical examination of lung cancer, a study with real-time PCR technology can be performed to assess the frequency of EGFR mutations, which is important in personalized patient therapy.

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